

Planar Low-Cost Microwave Ring Resonator Temperature Sensor using a PDMS Active Layer

Zabdiel Brito-Brito ^{#1}, Jesús Salvador Velázquez-González[#], Fermín Mira[#], Yi Wang[§], Ignacio Llamas-Garro ^{#2}

[#] Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/CERCA), 08860 - Castelldefels, Spain

[§] School of Engineering, The University of Birmingham, B15 2TT- United Kingdom

{¹ zbrito, ²illamas}@cttc.es

Abstract — In this work, preliminary results regarding a radio frequency planar low-cost temperature sensor, with potential for integrated sensing and communications are described. The sensor is based on a ring resonator onto which a layer of PDMS is added as the sensor active layer, allowing resonant frequency shift according to varying temperature, since the dielectric constant of the PDMS changes when exposed to different temperatures. The combination of a ring resonator with a layer of PDMS on top allows the development of a thermal sensor using microwave signals, such as those used for communications. The resonant frequency changes at a rate of 1 MHz per degree Celsius. The resonant frequency of the ring resonator alone at room temperature was designed to resonate at 4 GHz. This work is proof of concept towards integrated sensing and communication components.

Keywords — PDMS; Ring Resonator; Sensor, temperature; VNA.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ring resonators are widely used in microwave-based sensing applications for material characterization, including the detection of temperature-induced changes in dielectric properties [1]. Electromagnetic fields interact with materials, enabling the measurement of physical parameters across a broad frequency range. The microstrip ring resonator is a compact, cost-effective, and highly sensitive planar device extensively employed in communication systems, biomedical applications, and environmental monitoring [2]. Its operational principle is based on the propagation of electromagnetic waves along a conductive ring structure, generating standing wave patterns corresponding to specific resonance frequencies [2]. On the other hand, polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) is a material that enables wireless and chip-less electromagnetic sensing techniques, and thus allows for cost-effective and portable measurement setups, expanding practical applications [3].

The development of temperature sensors using PDMS and microwave circuits has seen significant advancements in recent years. PDMS, a versatile polymer, has become a popular material for temperature sensing applications due to its unique properties and compatibility with microwave technology. PDMS-based temperature sensors have been developed using various approaches [4]. One notable method involves the integration of PDMS with microwave circuits to create a capacitive dielectric temperature sensor. These sensors utilize PDMS loaded with conductive fillers such as copper, graphite, and milled carbon fiber powders [5]. These sensors have been successfully utilized in biomedical

monitoring, automotive systems, and industrial environments where real-time and wireless temperature sensing is required [6].

This work focuses on a very low-cost and simple fabrication solution by embedding a PDMS layer directly on top of a microstrip ring resonator. The PDMS acts as the active sensing layer, its temperature-dependent dielectric properties enable temperature sensing. As the temperature changes, the dielectric constant of PDMS varies, leading to shifts in the resonance frequency response of the sensor. This effect forms the basis of the proposed PDMS-based ring resonator temperature sensor. By precisely measuring the frequency shift, accurate temperature monitoring can be achieved.

By leveraging the properties of PDMS within microstrip ring resonator structures, we have developed a very-low-cost temperature sensor with the scope of sensing temperature using microwave signals, such as those used for communications. This integration represents a promising approach for integrated communications and sensing, offering robust performance, ease of fabrication and integration with other components and subsystems.

The integration of PDMS as a sensing layer over a ring resonator is successfully performed in this work. PDMS, known for its flexibility, thermal stability, and compatibility with microwave technology, has been widely utilized in various temperature-sensing applications, mainly at optical wavelengths. The combination of PDMS with microwave resonators, particularly ring resonators, is proof of concept towards integrated sensing and communication devices.

Section II describes the design and simulation results of the microwave ring resonator temperature sensor using PDMS as the active layer. Section III describes fabrication and measurement results of the sensor. And section IV presents the conclusion of this work.

II. DESIGN AND SIMULATION RESULTS

Microstrip ring resonators typically consist of a circular or ring-shaped conductive strip on a dielectric substrate. The resonator operates based on the principle that electromagnetic waves propagate along the ring, creating standing wave patterns at specific resonant frequencies [2]. In this work, the microstrip ring resonator was designed using an Arlon 25N substrate with thickness of 0.76mm, $\tan\delta=0.0025$ and $\epsilon_r=3.38$.

The ring resonator without considering the PDMS layer was designed to resonate at 4 GHz.

The sensor in this work consists of a planar weakly coupled ring resonator with a 2 mm layer of PDMS (T_{PDMS}) on top of the resonator, as shown in Fig. 1, where Fig. 1a shows the top view of the device denoting dimensions, and Fig. 1b shows a 3D view of the proposed temperature sensing device. The proposed temperature sensing device dimensions are provided in Table 1, according to Fig. 1a.

Fig. 1. Microstrip ring resonator temperature sensor with an embedded PDMS layer on top. (a) top view and sensor dimensions. (b) 3D view.

The microstrip ring resonator is used to make a temperature sensor due to its high sensitivity and compact size, including the ease of integration of the PDMS active sensing layer, all patterned in one face of the substrate. The proposed temperature-dependent changes in the resonant frequency of the ring resonator are used to measure temperature variations.

Table 1. Sensor Dimensions.

Tag	Value	Units
S_{in}	250	μm
W_{in}	2	mm
D_{ring}	18.4	mm
W_{ring}	2	mm
S_{ring}	300	μm
W_{PDMS}	25	mm
T_{PDMS}	2	mm

The PDMS is placed on top of the ring resonator to sense temperature variations. The ring resonator was designed to resonate at 3 GHz with PDMS on top.

III. FABRICATION AND MEASUREMENTS RESULTS

The microstrip ring resonator was fabricated using an Arlon 25N substrate fabricated with a LPKF c100hf CNC station. Then a 2 mm layer of PDMS (T_{PDMS}) is cured directly on top of the resonator using a rectangular 3D printed mold as shown in Fig. 2. Once the PDMS is cured the mold is removed. Fig. 3 shows the fabricated microstrip ring resonator sensor with the cured PDMS layer on top. SMA connectors were used to measure the S-parameters. The total device area is 5 cm \times 4 cm.

Fig. 2. Rectangular 3D printed mold for curing the PDMS layer on top of the resonator.

Fig. 3. Fabricated microstrip ring resonator sensor with the PDMS active layer on top.

The proposed sensor simulation and measurement results according to design parameters in Fig. 1a and Table 1, considering the sensor device with and without the PDMS active layer are shown in Fig 4.

Fig. 4. Simulation and measurement results comparison of the proposed temperature sensor with and without the PDMS layer on top (room temperature).

The first step of the measurements was comparing the effect of the PDMS on the ring resonator at room temperature shown in Fig. 4. The measured results are in good agreement with the simulated results. It is apparent from Fig. 4 that a resonant frequency variation of 1 GHz is observed between the resonator with air and PDMS layer on top.

An automated experimental setup is used to perform sensor characterization and measurements and involves a thermal chamber and network analyzer controlled using MATLAB, as shown in Fig. 5.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. Experimental setup (a) thermal chamber, VNA and computer data acquisition (b) sensor inside the thermal chamber.

The automated scattering parameter results obtained with this proof of concept are shown at -30, 25 and 60 degrees in Fig. 6, where a resonant frequency variation of 90 MHz is observed from the measurements.

Fig. 6. Measurement results comparing different temperature values

Table 2 shows the sensor resonant frequency according to different temperatures. Since the dielectric constant of PDMS changes with temperature, the resonant frequency of the resonator changes at a rate of 1 MHz per degree Celsius.

Table 2. Sensor resonant frequency according to temperature.

Temperature (°C)	Resonant frequency (GHz)
-30	3.005
0	3.020
25	3.040
40	3.060
60	3.095

Fig. 7 shows the frequency shifts obtained by post-simulation according to the experimental result, where the resonant frequency variation of 90 MHz is observed, corresponding to the PDMS dielectric constant values of 2.83 and 2.63, for -30 and 60 degrees Celsius respectively.

The PDMS dielectric constant changes at a rate of 0.0022 per degree Celsius. In [7] a rate of 0.0046 per degree Celsius was reported for the same temperature range but using a different sensor design, consisting of two types of TE- and TM-mode cylinder resonators with PDMS disks. The measurement results in Fig. 6 are in good agreement with the simulated results in Fig. 7.

IV. CONCLUSION

This work introduces preliminary results on a proof-of-concept device for temperature sensing, the sensor circuit can be potentially integrated in future 6G integrated sensing and communication systems.

Future work includes the development of higher sensitivity devices operating in the FR3 band. Investigation is still to be conducted regarding the PCB thermal expansion impact on overall sensor response.

Fig. 7. Post-simulation results with varying PDMS dielectric constant values.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been funded by Horizon Europe SNS-JU under the 6G-REFERENCE project (Grant Agreement: 101139155). This work is supported by the Generalitat de Catalunya under grant 2021 SGR 00772.

REFERENCES

- [1] Alahnomi RA, Zakaria Z, Yussof ZM, Althuwayb AA, Alhegazi A, Alsariera H, Rahman NA. Review of Recent Microwave Planar Resonator-Based Sensors: Techniques of Complex Permittivity Extraction, Applications, Open Challenges and Future Research Directions. *Sensors* (Basel). 2021 Mar 24;21(7):2267. doi: 10.3390/s21072267. PMID: 33804904; PMCID: PMC8036408.
- [2] Masrakin K, Ibrahim SZ, Rahim HA, Azemi SN, Soh PJ, Tantiviwat S. Microstrip Sensor Based on Ring Resonator Coupled with Double Square Split Ring Resonator for Solid Material Permittivity Characterization. *Micromachines*. 2023; 14(4):790. <https://doi.org/10.3390/mi14040790>.
- [3] Bao J, Markovic T, Brancato L, Kil D, Ocket I, Puers R, Nauwelaers B. Novel Fabrication Process for Integration of Microwave Sensors in Microfluidic Channels. *Micromachines* (Basel). 2020 Mar 19;11(3):320. doi: 10.3390/mi11030320.
- [4] Sharma PK, Chung JY. Evaluation of Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) as a Substrate for the Realization of Flexible/Wearable Antennas and Sensors. *Micromachines* (Basel). 2023 Mar 26;14(4):735. doi: 10.3390/mi14040735.
- [5] King B, Bruce N, Wagih M. Large-Area Conductor-Loaded PDMS Flexible Composites for Wireless and Chipless Electromagnetic Multiplexed Temperature Sensors. *Adv Sci* (Weinh). 2025 Jan 28 doi: 10.1002/advs.202412066.
- [6] Wagih M, Shi J, Li M, Komolafe A, Whittaker T, Schneider J, Kumar S, Whittow W, Beeby S. Wide-range soft anisotropic thermistor with a direct wireless radio frequency interface. *Nat Commun*. 2024 Jan 11;15(1):452. doi: 10.1038/s41467-024-44735-z.
- [7] Sharma, Praveen Kumar, Navneet Gupta, and Plamen I. Dankov. "Analysis of Dielectric Properties of Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) as a Flexible Substrate for Sensors and Antenna Applications." *IEEE Sensors Journal* 21, no. 17 (September 2021): 19492–504. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2021.3089827>.